

Classic Oceanic Crustal Section Recovered by Alvin Submersible Divers from the Puerto Rico Trench North Wall

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Abstract

After a retrofit for science applications at hadal ocean depths, the human occupied vehicle (HOV) Alvin was certified in July 2022 and verified for science applications on cruise AT50-2 in July-Aug 2022 with dives in the Puerto Rico trench. Anticipated (as of this writing) dives at the Mid Cayman Spreading Center occur next. A diverse and multidisciplinary team selected to represent a wide array of vehicle applications, career stage, and submersible experience participated in the expedition. Here we describe discoveries made during two dives on the first leg of AT50-2, which occurred at two different sites along the north wall of the Puerto Rico trench, due north of Puerto Rico near 20 °N, 66 °W. Outcrops of ca 105 and 112 Myr old, slow-spreading oceanic lithosphere formed at the Mid-Atlantic Ridge is exposed by faulting before the lithosphere descends underneath the Caribbean Plate (cf. Klein et al. J. Pet. 58, 2017 and references therein). Previous expeditions of the R/V Chain, R/V Robert Conrad, and R/V Eastward recovered igneous basement rocks and overlying sedimentary rock, including variably altered basalt, gabbro, and peridotite (Perfit et al. Mar. Geol. 34, 1980 and therein). Two Alvin dives in 2022 (dive 5090 and 5091) began at >6 km water depths, encountering excellent exposures of intrusive, dike, and extrusive crustal structures on steep rock faces of roughly 500m elevation, from which specimens of a classic oceanic crustal section were collected (e.g., weathered gabbro, plagiogranite, microcrystalline basalt, hydrothermally overprinted basaltic breccia, and sedimentary (cap) rock. This presentation will discuss the geological observations on the dives, the strengths and weaknesses of using Alvin in this setting, and the implications for future studies of this type using manned submersibles.

Puerto Rico Trench North Wall Rock Specimens collected by Humans in the Alvin Submersible at >6000m water depth on NSF-funded expedition AT50-02, Jul-Aug 2022 [photos by Ken Rubin]

Plain language summary

An expedition to test the usability of the submersible Human Occupied Vehicle Alvin at Hadal ocean depths for a wide array of science applications was conducted in Summer 2022. During these dives, rock exposures of ancient ocean crust, originally formed at the Mid Atlantic Ridge, were investigated in the North Wall of the Puerto Rico trench. This presentation will discuss the scientific implications of the specimens recovered as well as challenges of using the vehicle at these depths for geoscience activities.